

Synthesis of 4-Coumarinyl-2-Sulphanilamido-Thiazoles

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The synthesis of four new 4-coumarinyl-2-amino-thiazoles and their sulphonamides is reported. Their biological activity is studied.

From the therapeutic point of view, thiazole derivatives are of considerable interest because of their utility in the treatment of various diseases. Various sulpha thiazole derivatives¹⁻⁸ are widely used as bactericidals. Coumarins are also known for their physiological activity. It was, therefore, thought that the introduction of coumarinyl nucleus in 2-sulphanilamido-thiazole is likely to produce active compounds. With this view the work of the synthesis of 4-coumarinyl-2-sulphanilamido-thiazoles was undertaken.

4-Coumarinyl-2-amino-thiazoles have been prepared by condensing acetyl coumarins with thiourea in presence of a halogen⁹⁻¹³.

The following *o*-hydroxy-acetyl coumarins were used for the preparation of 4-coumarinyl-2-amino-thiazoles (Table 1).

- a) 4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-coumarin.
- b) 4-Methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl-coumarin.
- c) 4-Methyl-5-hydroxy-6-acetyl-coumarin.
- d) 4 : 7-Dimethyl-5-hydroxy-6-acetyl-coumarin.

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TABLE I

4-Coumarinyl-2-amino-thiazoles

Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Calculated		Found	
			C%	H%	C%	H%
1. 4-[6'-(4'-Methyl-5'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-amino-thiazole	230	40	56.93	3.650	56.31	3.913
2. 4-[8'-(4'-Methyl-7'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-amino-thiazole	257	30	56.93	3.650	56.49	3.811
3. 4-[8'-(4'-Methyl-6'-ethyl-7'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-amino-thiazole	269	50	59.61	4.635	59.36	4.807
4. 4-[6'-(4' : 7'-Dimethyl-5'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-amino-thiazole	190	40	58.33	4.167	57.98	4.416

4-Coumarinyl-2-amino-thiazoles prepared from the above coumarins were condensed with *p*-acetamido-benzene sulphonyl chloride, in dry pyridine and the N⁴-acetyl derivatives formed were hydrolysed to the corresponding sulphonamide (Table II and III).

R₁ = substituted hydroxy-coumaryl.

Infrared absorption spectra of the above compounds showed bands near 1470, 1530, 3350 and 3450 cm⁻¹ for thiazole ring, 1570, 1670 and 1720 cm⁻¹ for coumarinyl nucleus, 1170 and 1330 cm⁻¹ for S = O stretching, 1265 and 3070 cm⁻¹ for phenolic group and 1600 cm⁻¹ for primary amino group.

TABLE II

4-Coumarinyl-2-(N⁴-acetyl sulphanilamido)-thiazoles

Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Calculated		Found	
			C%	H%	C%	H%
1. 4-[6'-(4'-Methyl-5'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-(N ⁴ -acetyl-sulphanilamido)-thiazole.	188	60	57.40	3.872	56.84	4.309
2. 4-[8'-(4'-Methyl-7'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-(N ⁴ -acetyl-sulphanilamido)-thiazole.	216	55	57.40	3.872	57.77	4.450
3. 4-[8'-(4'-Methyl-6'-ethyl-7'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-(N ⁴ -acetyl-sulphanilamido)-thiazole.	186	60	59.10	4.496	58.84	4.817
4. 4-[6'-(4' : 7'-Dimethyl-5'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-(N ⁴ -acetyl-sulphanilamido)-thiazole.	198	65	58.28	4.195	58.06	4.386

TABLE III

4-Coumarinyl-2-sulphanilamido-thiazoles

Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Calculated		Found	
			C%	H%	C%	H%
1. 4-[6'-(4'-Methyl-5'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-sulphanilamido-thiazole.	157	40	57.42	3.779	57.51	3.920
2. 4-[8'-(4'-Methyl-7'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-sulphanilamido-thiazole.	237	50	57.42	3.779	57.23	4.125
3. 4-[8'-(4'-Methyl-6'-ethyl-7'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-sulphanilamido-thiazole.	260	45	59.29	4.474	58.78	4.729
4. 4 [6'-(4' : 7'-Dimethyl-5'-hydroxy-coumarinyl)]-2-sulphanilamido-thiazole.	213	30	58.39	4.136	58.19	4.334

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Coumarinyl-2-amino-thiazole (Table I): A mixture of *o*-hydroxy-acetyl-coumarin (1.0 mole), thiourea (2.0 moles) and iodine (1.0 mole) was heated in an oil bath at 110–120° for 12 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and washed repeatedly with ether. It was then dissolved in a little quantity of boiling water. The aqueous solution was filtered hot. The resulting solution was treated with concentrated ammonia solution. The pale yellow solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol repeatedly to a constant melting point.

4-Coumarinyl-2-(N⁴-acetyl-sulphanilamido)-thiazole (Table II): A mixture of 4-coumarinyl-2-amino-thiazole (0.01 mole), *p*-acetamido-benzene sulphonyl chloride (0.015 mole) and pyridine (15 ml) was heated over a water bath for 15 minutes and kept at room temperature for 48 hrs. It was poured over ice containing little sulphuric acid. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water, and crystallised from alcohol after adding activated charcoal.

4-Coumarinyl-2-sulphanilamido-thiazole (Table III): 4-Coumarinyl-2-(N⁴-acetyl sulphanilamido)-thiazole (1 gm) was boiled with hydrochloric acid (15 ml. of 30%) and ethanol (2 ml) for 20–50 minutes. The hot reaction mixture was filtered and made alkaline with sodium bicarbonate. The solid obtained was filtered and washed with distilled water. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol after adding activated charcoal.

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

These 4-coumarinyl-2-sulphanilamido-coumarins and their N⁴-acetyl derivatives were tested for fungal inhibition and seed germination activity. Fungus used was *Alternaria solani*. 25 ml of 0.001 molar solution was used in each case. The percentage inhibition of growth, was above 70% in all cases. These samples were tested for the germination of mustard seeds. Sample No. 1, 3 (Table II) and 3 (Table III) inhibit the growth completely, while sample No. 1 and 4 (Table III) showed 10% growth only.

8-(2-Amino-4-thiazolyl)-6-ethyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-coumarin decreased the growth of *Anti-Trichinella Spiralis* worms by 1.2%, while the other compounds were found to be inactive when a mouse was given a dose of 50 mg/kg.

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